

Figure S4. Expression of proteasome subunit

Proteasome subunit proteins were labeled on volcano plots (A) 1 h after OFC, (B) 2 h after OFC, (C) at symptom onset in the OFC-positive group, (D) 1 h after OFC, and (E) 2 h after OFC in the OFC-negative group.

Proteome analysis of serum samples was performed using four biological replicates for the OFC-positive group and five biological replicates for the OFC-negative group.